

Acknowledgement by Participant

We are researchers from the Australian National University, University of Saskatchewan (Canada), and the University of British Columbia (Canada).

This is a survey study that would take ~12 mins and would involve answering basic questions about your development practices regarding refactoring, and the challenges you often face during refactoring.

Please, read the Participant Information Sheet (PIS) before commencing the survey. The PIS is available at: [2022-237-Refactoring](#) (click to open in a new tab) and can be viewed in any browser.

I have read and understood the Participant Information Sheet and confirm that I am 18 years of age or older (or 21 years of age if your country considers you underage until then).

- Yes, I agree and I am 18 (or 21, as corresponds) years of age or older.
- No, I do not agree and/or I am younger than 18 (or 21, as corresponds) years old.

Screener Validation

What is your Prolific ID? *Please note that this response should auto-fill with the correct ID:*

Do you have *knowledge of software development techniques*, and have used **version control systems**?

- No
- Yes

Do you have Python programming knowledge?

- No
 Yes

Demographics

How many years of coding experience do you have? (Round to the closest full year)

- < 2 years
 2 - 5 years
 6 - 10 years
 11 - 15 years
 > 15 years

In addition to your Python programming skills, what is your skill level for the following languages? (1=novice, 5=expert, please specify other languages if relevant):

	1 = Novice	2	3	4	5 = Expert	N/A
Python	<input type="radio"/>					
Java	<input type="radio"/>					
C	<input type="radio"/>					
C++	<input type="radio"/>					
Javascript	<input type="radio"/>					
R	<input type="radio"/>					
Julia	<input type="radio"/>					

	1 = Novice	2	3	4	5 = Expert	N/A
Other <input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>					

When programming in Python, do you work with datascience projects (for example, scikit-learn, numpy, scipy, pandas, pytorch, keras, etc...) or with regular libraries (for example, django, flask, selenium, cherryypy, pygam, beeware, etc...)?

Rate below how much you use them on a scale from 0 (never used this), 1 (use it very infrequently), to 10 (most of your work is in this type of projects).

Note that the examples we mentioned above are *representative* examples, for you to understand the two "categories" we are considering. You could have worked with another library that still fits both criteria.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Work on data-science projects, using scikit-learn, numpy, scipy, pandas, pytorch, keras, etc...											<input type="text"/>
Work on "regular" or non-data-science projects, using django, flask, selenium, cherryypy, pygam, beeware, etc...											<input type="text"/>

Familiarity with Refactorings (1)

How familiar are you with **code refactoring**?

- I have never heard of it
- I have heard of it, but I am not so sure what it is
- I have a general understanding, but do not refactor/apply refactoring
- I have a good understanding, and sometimes or frequently refactor

How familiar are you with **code smells**?

- I have never heard of them
- I have heard about them, but I am not so sure what they are
- I have a general understanding, but do not use these concepts
- I have a good understanding, and use these concepts sometimes
- I have a strong understanding, and use these concepts frequently

Familiarity with Refactorings (2)

In the Python projects you worked on, have you...

	Yes	No	Don't Remember
...renamed anything in your code or project structure? For example, "The method test_weird_spectrum is renamed to test_weird_signal1D"	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
...moved any code from one location in the project to another? For example: "The method _get_rnn_unit from the class SequenceLabelingModel was moved to class GenericModel"	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Renaming something in your code or moving pieces of code between different locations (whether it is from one file to another, or to extract it into a function) is **refactoring**. Other examples of refactoring are the following: Method plot from the module hyperspy/drawing/_markers/vertical_line_segment.py in class VerticalLineSegment was moved to class MarkerBase of module hyperspy/drawing/marker.py class A was renamed to class _A The parameter [sequence_len_pt] was added to the method build_vocabulary from the module preprocessing.py

With this in mind, the following questions will enquire about these practices.

Refactoring Approaches

For the following **refactoring scenarios**, please select the most common approach used for it (if you did not use it, tick "N/A"). After that, characterize how frequently you used it (in total, regardless of the approach)?

Note that each of the options below have examples. These are just for illustrative purposes, and you may have worked with other names/modules/classes, but what matters in these examples is the refactoring type being applied.

	How was it done (the approach)?	How frequent (in total)?
Renaming a class, method, variable, or symbol. For example: "class A was renamed to class _A"	<input type="text" value=""/>	<input type="text" value=""/>
Extracting a method or a variable from existing code. For example: "The method _get_rnn_unit from module model.py in class SequenceLabelingModel is extracted from method build_model from module model.py in class SequenceLabelingModel"	<input type="text" value=""/>	<input type="text" value=""/>
Moving code to another file. For example: "method a_plot from the module line_segment.py was moved to marker.py"	<input type="text" value=""/>	<input type="text" value=""/>
Inlining a variable or method. For example: "The method _plot_xray from class EDSSpectrum is inlined into method plot from class EDSSpectrum"	<input type="text" value=""/>	<input type="text" value=""/>
Changing the signature of an existing function. For example: "The return type of method get_tf_config from the module config.py in class LocalConfig is updated"	<input type="text" value=""/>	<input type="text" value=""/>
Moving a method up or down the class hierarchy. For example: "method a_plot from class VerticalLineSegment was moved to parent class MarkerBase"	<input type="text" value=""/>	<input type="text" value=""/>

	How was it done (the approach)?	How frequent (in total)?
Other <input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>

What challenges do you often face when trying to perform specific refactorings? Try to be as detailed as possible.

Note that you need to write meaningful insights on each of the boxes--this will be validated.

- >> Renaming a class, method, variable, or symbol. For example: "class A was renamed to class _A"
- >> Extracting a method or a variable from existing code. For example: "The method _get_rnn_unit from module model.py in class SequenceLabelingModel is extracted from method build_model from module model.py in class SequenceLabelingModel"
- >> Moving code to another file. For example: "method a_plot from the module line_segment.py was moved to marker.py"
- >> Inlining a variable or method. For example: "The method _plot_xray from class EDSSpectrum is inlined into method plot from class EDSSpectrum"
- >> Changing the signature of an existing function. For example: "The return type of method get_tf_config from the module config.py in class LocalConfig is updated"
- >> Moving a method up or down the class hierarchy. For example: "method a_plot from class VerticalLineSegment was moved to parent class MarkerBase"
- >> Other

Why do you refactor? Please, select the appropriate frequency for each of the reasons below.

I generally refactor...

	Almost every day	Every week	Once or twice a month	Never
To move classes, methods, attributes (or other code elements) to appropriate container (e.g., a class to another package, an attribute to another class, a method to another file/class).	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
To eliminate dependencies	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
To remove duplication	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	Almost every day	Every week	Once or twice a month	Never
To eliminate unnecessary or deprecated methods, attributes, or classes	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
To simplify or allow extension or reuse of method, attribute, or class	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
To improve readability (including enforcing naming consistency)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
To preserve backward compatibility (namely, to allow older versions to continue using an element)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
To inline or remove methods that are now too trivial to be kept apart	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
To remove code smells that I detected (either automatically or manually).	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other <input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

What challenges have you faced when refactoring to remove code smells?

Note that if you are seeing this question then it is mandatory for you. Not completing this will be considered a poor quality response.

Attention Question! Please select *strongly agree* to validate your participation.

- Strongly disagree
- Somewhat disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Somewhat agree
- Strongly agree

Refactoring Tools

How familiar are you with the following IDE's refactoring features?

IDE is the Integrated Development Environment, such as PyCharm, DataSpell, IDLE, Spyder, PyDev, Eclipse, Visual Studio, among many others.

	Don't know about it	Know about it, but don't use it	Used it in the past, but will not use it again	Use it sometimes (less than weekly)	Use it regularly (almost every day)
Rename file, class, method, symbol, etc.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Extract method, variable, component, etc.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Move	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Inline variable or method	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Change signature	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Pull Up or Push Down attribute/class	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other <input style="width: 150px; height: 15px;" type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Can you characterize how much of the refactoring you perform is manual, IDE-assisted, or combined?

	Almost every day	Every week	Once or twice a month	Never
Manual	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
IDE-Assisted	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Combined	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Why do you refactor manually rather than using the IDE-assisted refactoring? Please read the statements below, and select how much you agree with each.

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree	N/A
I do not trust automated support for complex refactoring.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The automated refactoring was unnecessary, because the refactoring was trivial and faster/simpler to do it manually	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The required modification was not supported by the IDE.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am not familiar with the refactoring capabilities of my IDE.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
At the moment of refactoring, I did not realize that I could use the IDE for it.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other (please state) <input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

If you ever used IDE-assisted refactoring, what challenges have you encountered? Did any of this led you to avoid using these functionalities?

Note that if you are seeing this question then it is mandatory for you. Not completing this will be considered a poor quality response.